

BRAND REPOSITIONING: EFFECT ON PRODUCT LIFE CYCLE EXTENSION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Brand image repositioning, Brand personality Repositioning and Intangible Brand Repositioning are the study predictors. The population of the study are the marketers and repairers of phones accessories in St. Michael's GSM Market Aba, Abia State of Nigeria. A sample size of 185 drawn from the population constituted the respondents. Structured questionnaire was used to elicit relevant data from the respondents. After the analysis of data collected from the respondents and the testing of the study hypotheses, it was established that the predictors; Brand image repositioning, personality repositioning and intangible repositioning respectively has significant positive effect on product life cycle extension. It was therefore concluded that product Brand repositioning has significant effect on elongating the life cycle of a product. Major recommendations are that adoption of image reposition, personality reposition and intangible repositioning should be upheld to prolong the life cycle of a product.

Keyword: image repositioning, personality repositioning, intangible repositioning, effect, product life cycle extension, marketers, phones.

Introduction

Product brand positioning is very important to an organization as is essentially used to attract patronage. Chiendo and Oguanobi (2023) proclaimed that a firm's, strategic position choice has significant implications in a competitive market environment. Product branding is very important to organizations. Abugu (2015) described a brand as a name or mark intended to identify the product of one seller or sellers and differentiate it from competing product. Building strong brands has become a marketing priority for many organisations as strong brands yield a number of marketing advantages (Steve and Kevin, 2003) Effective branding makes a product more visible, identifiable and memorable. Brand is among the leading valuable assets of an organization. More often than not, a brand begins to loss its value and visibility, thus resulting to loss of sales, profit and competitive advantage and among the strategic options available for the Marketers is brand repositioning, Product positioning can be described as designing and placing a company's product image in that part of the market or target's

mind where it will have most favourable reception or where its reception will be better compared to that of the competitors. (Abugu, 2014) product repositioning is all about way of changing the thoughts customers associate with the brands. It is targeted at changing the prospects perception of the brand to make it seem more appealing. The importance magnifies when applied in a business suffering from bad, confusing or non-existent image or if the business is altering its strategic direction significantly. Gaurav (2020) aver that brand repositioning is ideal way for every business to innovate, reinvigorate, update recalibrate or just simply fend off the competition to highlights its supremacy as well as the unique selling proposition. In the views of Rahutama et al (2019) if the brand image is positive, then consumers will certainly make repeat purchase. Repositioning or strategic brand alternation can give brands significant advantage by making them relevant and aiding to stand out from the competitors. Differentiating brand repositioning from re-branding, Allison (2019) stated that brand repositioning focuses on the customer perception of brand relative to the major competitions, involving changes in the brand promise and personality, whereas rebranding associates itself with the looks or aesthetic of a brand to include changing the brand elements such as name, logo, tag line font or icons. Product life cycle is all about the stages a product undergoes from the time it is introduced into the market to the time it is withdrawn. It is the sales history of a product from the time it is introduced into the market to the decline, saturated or withdrawn stage. The product life cycle stage are; introductory stage, growth, maturity and decline stages. The growth stages is the peak in terms of sales volume, profit, competitive advantage and relative market share. The product life cycle management is the various but succession of strategies by business management as a product goes through its life-cycle. The conditions in which a product is sold changes over time and must be managed so that it goes through its succession of stages. It has been suggested that product repositioning is most appropriate at the maturity or decline stages of a product life-cycle. The propents are of the view that in the maturity stage repositioning can help revitalize sales and extend the product's life by targeting new segments. Whereas at the decline stage, repositioning might serve as the last ditch effort to salvage the product possibly by spotting a niche market or altering its appeal.

Studies show that brand repositioning strategy include; image repositioning, intangible repositioning and tangible repositioning. It can as well span to brand personality repositioning. This study focuses on the repositioning of Android phone and the effect on its life cycle extension.

Despite the relevance of brand repositioning, study on the theoretical debate concerning it is sparce and empirical evidence regarding its effect is inconsistent. But can image repositioning, brand personality repositioning and intangible re-positioning assist a business at its point of product brand sales decline, loss of customers, stagnant benefit and competition exert significant positive effect on the extension of product life cycle? was based on this, that this study was set to interrogates the effect of brand repositioning on the extension of life cycle of Android phones as a step towards addressing some research gaps. We therefore hypothesize that;

- Brand image repositioning has no significant relationship with Android brand phone lifecycle extension.

- There is no significant relationship between brand personality repositioning and Android brand phone life cycle extension
- Intangible brand re-positioning has no significant relationship with Android brand life cycle extension.

Review of Related literature

Conceptual Review

Brand image Repositioning

Brand image is used to portray the current mind set of customers about a brand, a reflection of what the brand stands for at present in the mind of the customer. Asish (2022) stated that brand image is a unique group of associations which creates a perception about an offering within the minds of the target customers. It is a bundle of functions and mental connections with a brand that customers have (Shubhany 2018). Such associations in the mind of the customers shape the brand, also the character of the organization to which the brand is associated with. It has been evidenced based on studies, that if a customer is loyal to a brand, it becomes obvious that the customer has a positive image of the brand. Positioning is all about differentiating brand for effective competition and advantage. Image repositioning entails that the target market and product remain unchanged but the brand image of the product undergoes a change (Ps.//haranppa.education) Brand image repositioning is a tool for getting a company back to track (Jan, 2022) especially if the brand failed as is viewed as having lost its way, needed to freshen things up a bit so as to remain competitive. Studies have shown that a strong brand image help to build trust with customers, increase market share and drive sales.

Brand Personality Repositioning

Brand personality is act of giving human qualities to the brand. Brand personality repositioning is altering the current human quality to the brand position largely due to inability of the current position to meet intended objectives. Swaminalhan et al (2019) affirmed that the effect of brand personality on brand attachment purchase likelihood and brand choice depends on the attachment style of the consumer including anxiety and avoidance of features. Brand personality has positive outcome on sales volume and customer loyalty improvement (Lin and Huang, (2019) has provided a strategic tool for executive Marketing managers through which the relationship will be reinforced (Achourc & Boustama, 2010) Brand personality describes how an organization imbues a brand with human personality traits intended to create symbolic association that are strong unique as well as congruent to the customer (Freling & Forbe, 2005) targeted at enhancing brand performance by communicating desired symbolic meaning to the customer through the brand. Atimes it could be repositioned, when the current position of the brand does not attract desired patronage. Plumer (2000) contended that brand personality is critical to the understanding of brand choice among consumers. Van Rekom et al (2006) however argued that strong brand personality is invaluable in building brand equity where differentiation based on quality seems to be very little among competing firms. A firms quest for the brand personality repositioning is usually due to the failure of the current brand personality positioning.

Intangible Brand Repositioning

At the point of any product brand repositioning, just as in this study, a particular target market is the focus. At times, it is because the targeted market response to the brand fall short of expectations, thus calls for re-positioning to a new audience with the same product or service. That is what intangible repositioning is all about. Studies unveil that repositioning in Marketing refers to the process a brand goes through to adjust or overhaul its perception in the Market to better appeal to its target audience. It is basically to reposition the brand in the mind of the audience so that they see the brand and its offering as more viable option. Reposition of any type is basically a strategy to align to the organization/product or service with the existing or future market conditions (Wong & Merrilees 2007). It is a strategy by organization to change their service or product positioning in the Market. (Temiloe, 2017) Kinga (2022) stated that brand re-positioning such as intangible positioning could occur when the brand does not appeal to young generation. Studies aver that poor re-positioning strategy of any type could as well result to losing customers and diluting the strength of brand.

Product Branding

Keller (2003) aver that when a marketer creates a name, logo or symbol for a new product, a brand has been created. Rutler (2000) contended that branding should be viewed as a major issue in product strategy. American Marketing Association defines a brand as a name, term, sign, symbol or design or a combination of them, intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of the competitors. A brand is aimed at ensuring that product capacity transcend beyond its outward appearance and foster in a customer an evolutionary connection that goes beyond product satisfaction (De Charnatony & MC) Donald cited in Chao & Jiyan, 2011). Keller (2003) viewed that branding is the development of mental structures to aid customers in organizing their brand knowledge address, the range of consumer emotions and cognitive process.

Brand Equity

Kotler and Keller (2013) defined brand equity as the added value endowed on products and services. Brand equity according to Kevin (2008) may be reflected in the way consumers think, feel and act with respects to the brand, also as in the prices, market share and profitability the brand command. The power of a brand lies in what customers have heard, seen, read, learned, thought and as well felt over a time about the brand (Aaker, 1997). Kevin (2008) reported that customer based equity is the differential effect brand knowledge has on consumer response to the marketing of that brand. Kapfere and Laurent (1988) however, contended that based on research, in several product categories, (Wrilling pad, felt-tip pens, markers) buyers do not look at the brand when making choice. Aaker (2013) maintained that brand equity enhances the customers' ability to interpret and process information, improves confidence in the purchase decision and affects the quality the user experience. Studies show that brand equity has four dimensions, namely; brand loyalty, brand awareness brand associations and perceived quality each of which provides value to a firm/product in numerous ways.

Theoretical Framework

Two theories guide this study;

Brand repositioning theory

Theory of reasoned action

Brand Repositioning Theory

The concept of brand repositioning theory emerged from the evolution of branding and that of marketing principles around mid-20th Century. No single scholar was credited to have discovered it; rather many scholars and practitioners contributed to its development and popularity. Brand repositioning is a strategic marketing approach where a company alters its image and perceived value in the market place to better align with evolving consumer needs or to address a changing competitive Landscape.

Repositioning has to do with modifying various aspects of the brands identity and indeed the marketing mix for purposes of meeting consumer wants and needs.

Theory of Reasoned Action

Fisbin and Ajzen developed theory of reasoned action in 1975. The theory is used to predict how individuals will act based on their existing attitudes and behavioural intentions. It brings to bear that action taken is informed by the likely reward therein but if reverse manifests at any time, resistance or objection becomes obvious.

As a form of synthesis, the brand repositioning arise due to inability of the initial brand positioning to conform with the company objectives (reasoned action) thus anchoring the study on the two theories is deemed a perfect match.

Model for the study

Figure 2.1 Brand Repositioning strategy

Research Methodology

Research Design

Survey Method was adopted for the study

Area of the Study

The study was conducted in St. Michael’s GSM Market in Aba Abia State, Nigeria.

Population of the study

The study population comprised of Marketers and repairers of phones and the accessories in St. Michael's GSM market Aba, Abia state of Nigeria.

Sample size and Sampling Technique

Taro Yamane Formula was used to determine the sample size of 185 for the study. Convenience sampling method was used to select the study respondents.

Research Instrument

Structured questionnaire was the study instrument used to collect necessary information from the respondents. Responses to questions directed to the respondents were on five-point Likert scale.

Validity and Reliability of the Research Instrument

Face and content validity were used to validate the questionnaire. Reliability test of the instrument which yielded 0.8 was achieved through Cronbach alpha test and was considered adequate.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data collected from the respondents were presented in tables below and analysed.

Table 4.1: Mean Rating of Responses of Respondents on the relationship between the following brand image repositioning strategies and product life cycle extension

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	N	FX	\bar{X}	Decision
1	The new attractive screen attracts more customers	29	93	-	13	50	185	593	3.2	Accepted
2	Quality modification draw more buyers	97	82	-	2	4	185	821	4.4	Accepted
3	Price adjustment increases sales	58	91	-	34	2	185	724	3.9	Accepted
4	Improvement on phone accessories increases sales.	93	88	-	1	3	185	4.4		Accepted
5	Easy of phone uses keep and attract new customers	80	95	-	10	-	185	800	4.3	Accepted
Total	Mean								3.2	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 above shows the mean mark calculated from the response of the respondents on the relationship between image brand repositioning strategies and product life cycle extension in computer village Ikeja Lagos. Based on the decision rule if \bar{x} is below 2.5 it is considered rejected and if \bar{x} is 2.5 and above it is considered accepted. However, all the items in the table were accepted because they score the mean score of 2.5 and the overall mean is 3.2 it therefore indicates that image brand repositioning strategies has significant positive effect on product life cycle extension.

4.2 Mean Rating of Response of Respondents on the relationship between brand personality re-positioning features and product life cycle extension

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	S D	N	FX	\bar{X}	Decision
1	High quality phone leads to repeat purchase	95	6	-	21	9	185	766	4.1	Accepted
2	Phone with energy saving battery command more customers	90	8	-	5	4	185	804	4.3	Accepted
3	Phone with touch light gain customers loyalty	125	4	-	8	-	185	837	4.5	Accepted
4	Phone with multifunctionality expand customer base	98	8	-	1	1	185	834	4.5	Accepted
5	Many customer surge to purchase easy to use phone	71	10	-	5	9	185	774	4.2	Accepted
Tot al	Mean								4.3	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2 above shows the mean mark calculated from the response of the respondents on the relationship between brand personality repositioning features and product life cycle extension. Based on the decision rule, that if x is below 2.5 it is considered rejected and if x is 2.5 and above it is considered accepted. Since, all the items in the table were accepted because they score the mean score of 2.5 and the overall mean is 4.3 it therefore indicates that brand personality repositioning has significant positive effect on product life cycle extension.

4.3 Mean Rating of Responses of Respondents on the Relationship between intangibility repositioning strategies and product Life Cycle extension.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	N	FX	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Storage capacity is a big consideration for purchase intension	93	88	-	1	3	185	822	4.4	Accepted
2	Camera is among the attractive features when taking purchase action	80	95	-	10	-	185	800	4.3	Accepted
3	Ability of information search is a consideration when purchasing phone	101	80	-	-	-	185	837	4.5	Accepted
4	Durability of phone goes a long way in attracting and retaining customers	90	85	-	5	4	185	804	4.3	Accepted
5	Long information retention	125	49	-	8	-	185	837	4.5	Accepted
Total	Mean								4.4	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.3 above shows the mean mark calculated from the response of the respondents on the relationship between brand intangibility repositioning strategies and product life cycle extension. Based on the decision rule, that if x is below 2.5 it is considered rejected and if x is 2.5 and above it is considered accepted. As observed, the items in the table were accepted because the mean score is 2.5

and the overall mean is 4.4 it therefore indicates that brand intangibility repositioning has significant positive relationship with product life cycle extension.

Test of study Hypotheses

The results for the various tests of hypotheses, which were tested with the Linear Regression analysis and he results are presented below:

Test of Hypothesis One

Brand image repositioning has no significant relationship with Android brand phone life cycle extension.

Table 4.1.1 The Relationship between brand image repositioning and Product life cycle extension

Model	R	R Square	AdjustedRSquare	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					
					R Square Change	F Change	Df1	Df2	Sign.FChange	
1	.656 ^a	.431	.424	41126	431	68.798	1	9	.000	
Model	Sum of Squares		Df		MeanSquare	F	Sig			
1	Regression	11.636	1	11.636	68.798	.000 ^b				
	Residual	15.391	183	.169						
	Total	27.027	184							
Model	<u>Understandardized Coefficients</u>			<u>Standardized Coefficients</u>		T	Sig			
	B	Std. Error		Beta						
1 (Constant)	1.495	.248		.656	6.023					
Brand image	.540	.065			8.294					

a. Dependent variable: Product life cycle extension

Table 4.2.1 revealed that brand image repositioning has significant effect on product life cycle extension of 43.1% ($R^2=0.431$, $p=0.000$). relationship between brand image repositioning and product life cycle extension Aba, Abia State Nigeria, The study found that the regression model was the best fit for predicting the effect of brand image repositioning on product life cycle extension ($F=68.798$, $p=0.000$). Similarly, the study revealed that every unit change in brand image repositioning will significantly affect the variance in product life cycle extension 65.6% ($Beta=0.656$, $p=0.000$).

Test of Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between brand personality re-positioning and Android brand phone life cycle extension.

Table 4.2.2 The relationship between brand personality and Product life cycle extension on intention

Model	R	R Square	AdjustedRSquare	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	Df1	Df2	Sign.FChange
1	.674	.455	.449	.40249	.455	75.838	1	9	.000
Model	Sum of Squares		Df		MeanSquare	F	Sig		
1	Regression	12.284	1	12.286	75.838	.000 ^b			
	Residual	14.742	183	.162					
	Total	184	184						
Model	Understandardized Coefficients				Standardized Coefficients		T	Sig	
	B	Std. Error		Beta					
1 (Constant)	1.504	.236			6.379	.000			
Personality Brand image	.508	.058		.674	8.709	.000			

a. Dependent variable: Product life cycle extension.

Table 4.2.2 above revealed that brand personality repositioning has positive relationship with product life cycle extension by a variance of 45.5% ($R^2=0.455$, $p=0.000$).

This therefore shows that there is significant positive relationship between brand personality repositioning and product life cycle extension in Aba, Abia State Nigeria. Again the study found that the regression model was the best fit for predicting the effect of brand personality on product life cycle extension. In the same vain, the study revealed that every unit change in brand personality repositioning affect the variance significantly product life cycle extension by 67.4% ($Beta=0.674$, $p=0.000$).

Test of Hypothesis Three

Intangible brand repositioning has no significant relationship with Android phone life cycle extension

Table 4.2.3 The Relationship between brand intangibility and Product life cycle extension

Model	R	R Square	AdjustedRSquare	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	Df1	Df2	Sign.FChange
1	.733 ^a	.537	.532	.37087	.537	105.503	1	91	.000
Model	Sum of Squares		Df		MeanSquare	F	Sig		
1	Regression	14.511	1	14.511	105.503	.000 ^b			

Residual Total	12.516 27.027	143 184	.138		
Model	<u>Understandardized Coefficients</u>			<u>Standardized Coefficients</u>	
	B	Std. Error		Beta	T
1 (Constant)	1.184	.231	.733		5.123
Brand intangibility	.655	.064			10.271
					.000
					.000

a. Dependent variable: Product life cycle extension

Table 4.2.3 demonstrate that brand intangibility repositioning has effect on product life cycle by a variance of 53.7% ($R^2=0.537$, $p=0.000$). This therefore confirms that there is a significant positive relationship between brand intangibility repositioning and product life cycle extension in Aba, Abia State Nigeria.

The study equally found that the regression model was the best fit for predicting the effect of brand intangibility on product life cycle extension ($F=105.503$, $p=0.000$).

Similarly, the study revealed that every unit change in brand intangibility repositioning significantly affect product life cycle extension by 64.4% ($Beta=0.733$, $p=0.000$).

Discussion of Findings

The study discovered that image repositioning has significant positive effect on product life cycle extension as it relates to image repositioning, Grover (Grover 2019) contended that companies resort to product repositioning to improve image. This aligned with the outcome of the study. When the brand image improves it resonates an increased patronage for the brand, thereby extending the life cycle.

Supporting the outcome of the study as it affects the image and brand personality repositioning, Mishra and Choudhury (2013) aver that repositioning can improve brand image and personality of companies. In the view of Cross (2016) repositioning product later in life with a nostalgic collecting focus has become a big business. It was also found that brand personality repositioning has significant positive effect on product life cycle extension.

This study outcome on the relationship between brand personality repositioning and product life cycle extension conform with the result of the study conducted by Lin and Hung (2013) on the effect of brand personality repositioning which found out that brand personality repositioning has positive effect on sales volume and customer loyalty improvement. Freling and Forbe, (2005) contended that personality traits are strong unique and aligned to customer preference. Karrjaluoto, Munnukka and Salome (2016) stated that brand personality has been observed as instrumental and descriptive issues in identifying the inclinations attitudes and intentions of consumers and developing their brand loyalty. The findings of the study in this regard aligned with the views of Ladipo, Mordi and Iheanacho (2021) that business organisations should critically evaluate changing personality traits and identify the brands personality that will convey the right message to the customers through his or her personality to stimulate consumer desire and purchase for the company’s brands.

The study equally affirmed that intangibility repositioning has significant positive relationship with product life cycle extension.

The study findings on the relationship between intangible brand repositioning and product life cycle extension is in congruent with Kinga (2022) who affirmed that brand repositioning can occur when the brand does not appeal to young generation.

Killer and Lehmann (2006) proclaimed that brands serve as intangible assets of immense value, differentiating companies and propelling them towards long term success. Another support gained by this study findings is that of the study conducted by Rwamba et al (2023) who found that intangible repositioning which focuses on altering perceived value can significantly impact on sales by influencing, customer perception and bring positive brand associations. Research has confirmed that intangible branding encompassing brand image, reputation and customer experience significantly impacts sales by fostering trust, loyalty and perceived value.

Conclusion

The study was on the effect of brand repositioning on product life extension.

Brand image positioning, brand personality repositioning and intangibility brand re-positioning formed the predictors of the study. After the analysis of the data and the test of the study hypotheses, it was discovered that brand repositioning strategies has significant relationship with the product life cycle extension. Based on this, the researchers affirmed that brand image repositioning brand personality repositioning and intangibility brand repositioning respectively has significant positive relationship with product life cycle extension.

Recommendations

1. Marketers should engage in brand image repositioning to increase the life span of their products
2. Personality brand repositioning should be used as a strategy to extend product life cycle.
3. Intangibility brand repositioning should be used as a tool to elongate product lifecycle.

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